

Soul Conflict in Faisal Tehrani's Selected Novels

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Abstract

Faisal Tehrani is one of the prolific authors and active in producing various literary genres and excels as a novelist. The novels he produced included teenage novels and now produced more serious novels, in line with his maturity and maturity in his work. This study aims to analyze the soul conflict expressed in five of his selected novels, namely *Perempuan Politikus Melayu (PPM)*, *Manikam Kalbu*, *Surat-surat Perempuan Johor (SsPJ)*, *Tunggu Teduh Dulu (TTD)* dan *Bahlut*. This psychic conflict will be discussed in three aspects, namely the causes of conflict triggers, conflict manifestations and conflict resolution. This soul conflict will be examined through the main characters and the conflicting side characters. This study uses a qualitative methodology because it involves careful reading and interpretation of written sources. The findings of the study show that Faisal Tehrani's novels are loaded with various psychological elements to express the author's feelings, messages and perspectives on human problems that occur based on the author's point of view.

Keywords: Novel, subject, conflict, manifestation and resolution.

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Introduction

The author's relationship with his environment is very familiar in producing a work. The ideas and thoughts that are worked on are sourced from experience, observation, reading and study so that it becomes more interesting and effective to be presented to the audience. Accordingly, the author is a creative human being who has the ability to think, imagine and speak to produce works whether poetry, novels, short stories or dramas. Man and his society become a very important raw material to the author (Sohaimi Abdul Aziz, 2011). The author who knows himself and all aspects of humanity will continue to interpret his work on human beings and their problems, human beings and communication either in monologue or dialogue, human transformation either physically or spiritually and other aspects of human beings that are futuristic, loving, nostalgic, institutional and others (Azhar Hj. Wahid, 2013). Meanwhile, the author and the literary work themselves have the ability to work on all fields and disciplines of knowledge which is then processed with beautiful language with so many laces and captivating rhythms, then it is easier to develop pure values and the value of knowledge and science is one of the core that underlies pure values (Azhar Hj. Wahid, 2012).

According to Shahnnon Ahmad (1994), literature should also be a serious thinker, who through his work is able to enlighten his views and views of readers, who matures his life and the lives of others who have context with his work and bring himself and readers to contemplate this secret angle of life. The development of human life is reflected through thoughts that are translated into various forms of expression (Sohaimi Abdul Aziz, 2001). The essence of literature is man. We give meaning to the human heart which is the headquarters of humanity; either in terms of physiology, physical, psychological, spiritual, sociological or social aspects of it (Shahnnon Ahmad, 1994). According to him, literature is in no way separate from man and nature. Therefore, the author can not escape from the influence of race (race) and character (character), environment (milieu) and community circle as well as other needs related to residence, traditions, customs, hopes, spirit, attitudes and tendencies.

Research Objectives

Specifically, this study has the following objectives:

1. To identify the causes of psychic conflict in selected novels written by Faisal Tehrani.
2. Analyze the manifestations of psychic conflict based on psychological theories expressed in selected novels by Faisal Tehrani.
3. Analyze the resolution of psychic conflict based on psychological theory in selected novels by Faisal Tehrani

Literature Review

Mohd Faisal bin Musa or known by the pen name as Faisal Tehrani was born in Kuala Lumpur on August 7, 1974. Implicitly, Faisal Tehrani is difficult to understand by his own friends because he has a rather mysterious and ambitious personality (Ummi Hani, 2006). As such, he has a nature that does not follow the opinion of others and holds to the principle that everything he does must be done according to his responsibility to society. As a writer who has high ambitions in elevating the world of writing homeland, he is willing to travel to every corner of the country such as Indonesia, the Middle East, Europe and Turkey to enrich his writing talent (Wan Zaliha binti Wan Othman, 2013). The determination and success of producing quality work has strengthened Faisal Tehrani's position as a caliber author in the country's literary arena. As proof, he is said to be one of the country's most active and talented writers for successfully producing quality works (Affandi Hassan, 2005). In the early creative process of involvement, Faisal Tehrani's writing style was influenced by Shahnnon Ahmad's writing style because he learned a lot and emulated the writing techniques of the writer (Wan Zaliha binti Wan Othman, 2013). To date, he has won various writing competitions organized by the government as well as the private sector. The highest award he won was the National Arts Award by the Government of Malaysia in 2006.

In an effort to introduce himself in the world of local writing, he has used various nicknames during the early stages of his writing. Among the names that have been used are Pasdaran e-Islam and Tun Mamat. However, the use of the name cannot show itself to be recognized. Even the average editor is not interested in the name. Realizing the situation, he used the name Faisal Tehrani and this name has appeared since he was still in school (Dewan Sastera, March 2007). Faisal Tehrani's name was obtained because he was influenced by the reading of Arabic books and books written by Iman Bukhari and other Islamic figures such as Malik Ben Nabi, Abu Hasan an Nadwi and Hassan al-Banna. Tehrani himself refers to an abbreviation of the word Tehran which is one of the tempat in the Middle East. The influence on the reading also caused Faisal Tehrani to tend to write on issues and problems such as history and religion.

Regarding his career, he used to work at Universiti Sains Malaysia (USM) and continued his master's degree in 1998. He resigned from his job at USM because he wanted to get involved in writing seriously or full time. To realize the interest in creative writing, he has been pursuing for his doctorate (PhD) in Natural Malay Civilization (ATMA), Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia (UKM). He graduated in 2010 and obtained a Doctor of Philosophy Degree in Islamic Literature by discussing the issue of Islamic phenomena with the thesis title "Islamic Literature: Phenomena, Discourse and Its Application in Malaysia and Indonesia". Through the conferment of the Doctor of Philosophy Degree has given an easy path to Faisal Tehrani to become a professional and knowledgeable writer. Now he works full-time as a lecturer at the Institute of Malay World and Civilization (ATMA), Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia.

Findings and Discussions

According to Hashim Awang (1984), conflict is a conflict or struggle between two parties. In modern works, internal conflict is also revealed, which is the chaos of the soul due to certain problems (Rahman Shaari, 1987). If human beings fail to store conflict and then tell it to others or are born unnoticed, it is considered neurosis, i.e. emotional conflict at the base of the soul (Mana Sikana, 1988). Safian Hussain et. al (1988) define conflict as a contradiction or struggle that arises from the state of interaction between two opposing forces in the plot of a story. Conflict is a stage that evokes elements of tension and that attracts attention in any form of fiction, whether drama, novel or short story.

Faisal Tehrani does apply soul conflict in his novels. In modern works, internal conflict is also revealed, which is the chaos of the soul due to certain problems (Rahman Shaari, 1987). If human beings fail to store conflict and then tell it to others or are born unnoticed, it is considered neurosis, i.e. emotional conflict at the base of the soul (Mana Sikana, 1988). According to Arena Wati (1996), a novel will not run away from its story development techniques; from meaning to problems and conflicts and to goals. In this case, each plot must be animated with a very key story factor, namely the role of the character, the dialogue of the character, the atmosphere of the story, the location and the environment. Therefore, the author must show how the conflict occurs, how the character speaks and so on.

Mental conflict analysis based on psychoanalytic theory in novels

This aspect of conflict was chosen because it is an element that is favored and expressed effectively in his novels. Although he was not a master of psychiatry or psychology, but was able to present various psychiatric conflicts in his novels. This conflict is highlighted through the characters he portrays. All characters whether male and female characters as well as teenagers up to the elderly have their own conflicts. Usually, these conflicts are associated with negative but sometimes the conflict faced also has a positive effect on a person.

Based on his novels, Faisal Tehrani does create and present various conflicts in his novels. Each of his novels carries a different conflict and there are also similarities of conflict that may be intentional. The conflict of the soul in his view is a stress that occurs within the self due to certain reasons. The causes that trigger this conflict are divided into two, namely internal and external causes. Conflicts that stem from internally are self -caused such as the existence of feelings of frustration, resentment, self -weakness and so on. While the source of conflict from the outside is due to the environment, peers, parents, poverty and so on.

The ability to work on the various elements of this conflict shows that Faisal Tehrani is not only a committed and dedicated author, but also an analyst of the complex life of his community. All the problems of society are seen not from the physical aspect but also the psychological aspect. He is able to convey the psychic aspects of the characters creatively and effectively so that he can provoke a reaction to the audience of readers of his novels. He carefully, prudently and carefully triggers conflict to enable the reader to accept, understand and appreciate something being conveyed. In this study will focus on the construction of conflicts against the characters in selected novels. The novels are part of the work of Faisal Tehrani, who is seen very clearly presenting conflicts to his characters. The psychic conflict analyzed is divided into three aspects, namely the causes that trigger the conflict, the manifestation of the conflict and the resolution or action to resolve the psychic conflict.

Analysis of mental conflict triggers

Internal or Intrinsic Factors

Conflict is an element of contradiction. Various forms of contradiction can be created. Among them are man with man, man with nature, man with society, man with himself and many more (Mana Sikana, 1988). According to Hashim Awang (1984) internal conflict is a contradiction in a human being, that is, a contradiction in his thoughts, feelings or morals. In the context of this study the internal conflicts created by the authors are due to self, frustration and loss.

Self Factor

In the context of this study, self refers to the internal and physical conditions possessed by the characters. This self or internal conflict exists due to several factors such as physical factors and lack of self. In his novels, psychic conflicts caused by self-factors are self-fault, self-physical condition or self-weakness, personal problems, and ambitions and so on. In the novel, PPM shows that physical factors that are already weak and have no effect cause mental conflict. This is illustrated through the characters of Haji Chenon, Jenny, and Mak Milah as well as Jora. This situation causes the characters to experience conflict to defend themselves, rights and get justice. In this novel, Haji Chenon faces psychological challenges as opposed to physical challenges. Haji Chenon is facing the toughest test in life to defend the rights, dignity and justice for himself and the village community in general. Haji Chenon is struggling with Datuk Zuri who wants to take the villagers' paddy land with a low value compared to the real market price. Due to his already weak, decrepit and influential condition, Haji Chenon was considered an opponent of the government for objecting to the acquisition of lands for national development projects. Similarly, Jora and Mak Milah suffered from stress because they were powerless to fight the parties involved in the acquisition of their paddy land. They are very sad, disappointed and moved to see the bulldozers exploring the paddy land to be used as an approved development site.

Apart from that, Faisal Tehrani showed that women are often in competition with men if they have superior characteristics. Salsabilan's nature and attitude as a person who is persistent, brave, resilient, and beautiful and looks perfect makes her a dream to marry him. It is this quality that is present in Salsabila so that it becomes a snatch and a mention to other individuals. This is the situation faced by the character Salsabila in TTD. This conflict exists after Kamal and Lam Phing Hai compete with each other to take her as their future wife. At the same time, Teh Sofia has kept her feelings for Kamil. Salsabila faces a dilemma to decide whether to choose Kamil or Lam Ping Hai because she does not want the friendship they built since childhood to end with her decision. In addition, Salsabila faces conflict with himself after realizing his actions slapped and terminated Sazli as his employee. This situation arose after Salsabila found evidence that it was not Sazli who tried to molest himself but Shahruzzaman. As a result, Salsabila felt very guilty and remorseful as well as restless thinking of action against Sazli. Salsabila felt very sorry for firing Sazli and uttered rather harsh words against Sazli without giving him a chance to hear his explanation.

In the novel, SsPJ also shows a conflict with himself by Ungku Nur. Ungku Nur suffered from stress because he never felt happy with his marriage to Norhishamudin. Ungku Nur married based on his father's choice and desire to strengthen his position in the political arena. Similarly, Norhishamudin was willing to marry her for the same purpose. This situation caused Ungku Nur to be in depression, sadness and a lot of hiding feelings. Ungku Nur's feelings became more uncertain when he was diagnosed with stage four cancer and after that Norhishamudin became more and more distant from him. However, Ungku Nur never told her family or husband about her family problems and cancer. Ungku Nur suffered mental and physical abuse by Norhishamudin's irresponsible attitude as a husband. Ungku Nur was not given service both outwardly and inwardly.

Bahlut's novel also shows Bahlut's character having a conflict with himself because he is of indigenous descent. The conflict within Bahlut existed after getting advice and help from teacher Zaiful. Cikgu Zaiful wants Bahlut to continue his studies and migrate to Kuala Lumpur. Bahlut felt ashamed, worried, doubtful and suspicious of other races because he was left behind from other races. While in Kuala Lumpur, Bahlut felt very embarrassed to live in Ust Zaidi's Muslim family. At school, Bahlut also faced conflict because he was often mocked and insulted by Razak. Razak considers himself and his tribe to be weak, backward and unwise.

Disappointment Factors

Disappointment refers to feelings of emptiness, resentment and sadness due to loss, failure and so on. Faisal Tehrani makes the element of frustration as a source of conflict in the novels PPM, 1515, SsPJ and Bahlut. For example, in the PPM novel, feelings of frustration are described in the characters of Irfan, Haji Chenon, Mak Milah, Jenny, Kasmariza and Chai Yinn. All of these characters experience soul conflict due to frustration in getting, achieving and expecting hope to come true. Feelings of frustration over love are a major cause of soul conflict. This can be observed in the characters of Irfan, Jenny, Chai Yin and Kasmariza. Irfan is described as very upset when his love and affection have been disappointed by Kasmariza. Irfan's character is described as experiencing a lot of disappointments in his life. Irfan is described as experiencing frustration in romance, the struggle to uphold justice and his career. Disappointment in romance occurs when Kasmariza initially falls in love with each other and is close to establishing a household. All Irfan's hopes were not fulfilled when Kasmariza chose another young man as his successor. Irfan's feelings are further hurt when the young man is not from a local youth but a foreign youth. Irfan's frustration increased when he failed to bring Datuk Zuri to court to receive the appropriate punishment for the atrocities committed against the villagers and Jenny. Next, frustrated with his job as a journalist who cannot be free to present something transparently as well as truthfully. This is because there is a certain power or influence that controls the press and they need to obey the instructions from

that party. This situation is contrary to the principles and tenets that became his philosophy. Therefore, Irfan is willing to resign as a journalist

The characters of Haji Chenon, Mak Milah, Jora, Jenny, Chai Yin, Leslie and Kasmariza also experienced humor. They keep their feelings and crave love from the same young man, namely Irfan. But Irfan rejects their feelings of love well and prudently. Similarly, Haji Chenon, Mak Milah and Jora were very disappointed when they failed to defend their paddy land from being taken to succeed in the development project that will be carried out. Leslie is also upset when the desire to take Jenny as a wife is unattainable because Jenny considers her an uncle and nothing more than that.

In TTD is described the frustration faced by Salsabila. Salsabila's character suffers from frustration from a number of reasons such as family problems, friends, leaders and failing to defend heritage land from being taken for development purposes. Salsabila's frustrating family problem is the attitude of her stepmother who has never treated herself well since childhood. Salsabila only got along with his stepmother after his father's death. Salsabila is disappointed with Shahruzzaman's attitude of living freely with friends, spending a lot of time, being lazy to work and quietly marrying Mimi. Salsabila's frustration with Shahruzzaman is increasingly felt when he tries to burn the papaya farm and desecrate it. Salsabila is disappointed with the attitude of her two friends, namely Lam Phing Hai and Kamal who have both fallen in love with her. As a result they have quarreled and the friendships built from childhood have been cracked as a result of the existence of that feeling. Salsabila was also disappointed with the attitude Teh Sofia had brought to herself at a time when she desperately needed Teh Sofia's help and support to manage the papaya farm. Teh Sofia also experienced disappointment after her feelings of love were rejected by Kamal.

Disappointment is also presented in SsPJ's novel. This feeling of disappointment was experienced by Ungku Nur. Ungkur Nur is disappointed due to her husband Norhishamudin's attitude and her father's action of marrying her to Norhishamudin. Throughout the marriage, Norhishamudin did not fulfill his responsibilities as a husband. Ungu Nur was not given attention, love and good service from Norhishamudin from outward and inward. Ungku Nur's feelings continued to be disappointed when Norhishamudin took a hands-off attitude after finding out that he was battling cancer.

In the novel Manikam Kalbu, the soul conflict experienced by Ziryab is also shown. Ziryab is described as feeling very upset with the attitude of his male friends who mocked and ridiculed his choice to major in sewing while other male colleagues chose the technical major. Ziryab's frustration was evident when he was accused of sending obscene messages to Cikgu Natasya. Ziryab felt very upset and sad because no one trusted him including teacher Natasya and ustaz Asmadi who were close to him. The feeling of disappointment in Ziryab continued to be felt when his grandmother died. The loss of his grandmother caused Ziryab's life to be like a bird with broken wings due to the loss of a place to depend on.

Feelings of frustration continue to be worked on in Bahlut's novel. This frustration stems from the destruction of the forest, the romance and the attitude of the leaders. Bahlut's character experiences conflict due to internal and external factors or his environment. The frustration experienced by Bahlut as a result of internal factors is the failure in romance. Bahlut feels very upset and sad after Kabut rejects his feelings towards him and assumes that Kabur has already received an application from Tiat. Kabut, on the other hand, rejects Bahlut's feelings of love because they are different ages and consider Bahlut as his younger brother. The external factors that triggered the conflict were the difficulty in dealing with illegal logging activities and wanting to bring the parties involved in illegal logging activities in their settlement areas to justice. The problem of illegal logging is difficult to deal with and takes a long time, because this problem starts from primary school Bahlut to entering secondary school as well as becoming a new successful athlete can be addressed.

Loss Factor

The loss that triggers conflict is the loss of something very dear, precious and dignified. Losing something important, loved and needed such as mother, father, grandmother and possessions will push a person into conflict. In the novels Faisal Tehrani has shown that the loss of something loved such as mother, father, friends, property and so on has caused conflict to the characters. For example in the novel PPM, TTD and Bahlut show that the loss of a loved one has triggered conflict to his characters. In the PPM novel, the characters of Haji Chenon, Mak Milah and Jora are shown experiencing a serious mental conflict due to the loss of paddy land. This is because the paddy land taken by the developer company is a very deserving legacy in their lives. Their frustration is exacerbated when they are compensated at a lower value than the actual market price.

Similarly in the TTD novel, the soul conflict of losing land is highlighted through the characters of Salsabila and Teh Sofia. Salsabila was very upset when the land left by his father which had been turned into a papaya plantation had to be handed over to the developer to make the development project a success. Disappointment was also due to their elected representative, Datuk Ghaffar not being able to defend the land belonging to Salsabila and the villagers from being taken for development purposes. In Bahlut, the conflict within Bahlut is due to the loss of his mother and father. This situation caused Bahlut to live a life alone and decide to finish school. Bahlut was in grief thinking of the fate of himself who lost

his place of livelihood. Meanwhile, in the novel *Manikam Kalbu*, it is shown that the loss of a loved one, namely his grandmother has caused Ziryab not to be eager to study due to the loss of a place to depend on and a successor to his parents.

External factor

Hashim Awang (1984) argues that external conflicts may be caused by such conflicts between humans and humans, or between humans and nature. In this study, it was found that several external factors trigger psychic conflict, namely cultural and environmental factors, family environment and socioeconomics of family, peers, politics and society.

Cultural and Environmental Factors

Culture refers to the way of life or behaviors of a group of people. It covers aspects such as customs, values, thought patterns, world views and philosophies. Usually this cultural practice will continue to be practiced and inherited from generation to generation in a society. The cultural conflict that Faisal Tehrani tries to highlight can be traced in the novels of *PPM* and *Bahlut*. Through the *PPM* novel the conflict stemming from this culture is portrayed through the characters Jenny and Kasmariza. Jenny's character is portrayed as a modern or urban woman adopting a very different way of life to the rural woman portrayed through Jora's character. Jenny's character experiences a cultural conflict when she meets Irfan who is from the village. Irfan's simple attitude and way of life, having pure values and adhering to religion caused Jenny to fall in love with Irfan. In addition, Kasmariza experienced conflict after marrying a foreign youth. Due to differences in customs, culture and thinking, the household he built did not last long. The psychological conflict experienced by Kasmariza is increasingly depressed after separating from her husband and also faced with the problem of claims on the custody of her children who are with her husband abroad.

Similarly, in *Bahlut's* novel, differences in religion, culture and thought bring mental conflict to *Bahlut*. Due to differences in religion, culture and environment, *Bahlut* refused to continue his studies in Kuala Lumpur. *Bahlut* is worried about the fate of himself who is different in religion from the family of *Zaiful's* brother who is Muslim. In addition, due to cultural, social and religious differences, conflicts arose between *Bahlut* and *Razak*. *Razak* has insulted him because he is an indigenous tribe that is still considered weak, sluggish, archaic and ignorant like other societies.

Environment, on the other hand, refers to something that is around a person, including the environment such as rivers, forests, schools, communities, buildings, oceans and so on. An imperfect environment will cause conflict to a person. This is presented in the novel *TTD* and *Bahlut*. In the *TTD* novel, the soul conflict experienced by *Salsabila* results from the environment. The cause of the problem of *Salsabila* which is faced with various environmental problems that affect the cultivation of papaya that is being cultivated. Flood conditions, pest attacks, insects and diseases have threatened the fruits and papaya trees that are producing their fruits. Meanwhile, in *Bahlut's* novel, the problem of *Bahlut's* new living environment has caused conflict to his soul. *Bahlut* migrated to Kuala Lumpur and lived with *Ust Zaidi's* family. *Bahlut* is in conflict to adjust to his new family and new school. Prior to that, the lives of *Bahlut* and the villagers were increasingly affected due to logging activities such as facing water, air pollution, loss of forest resources and security. The same goes for *Dew* and *Kabut* who experienced a mental conflict to adjust after migrating to Kuala Lumpur. They had to migrate and settle in Kuala Lumpur to save themselves from the *Tiat* and the *Tiat* people to avoid their crimes being exposed.

Family Environmental and Socio -Economic Factors of the Family

According to the anthropological definition, a family is a unit (group) made up of members who have a family. For *Frued* family as a combination of mother and father who live in the same house with or one or more children (*Azizi Yahaya et.al, 2005*). The family also consists of a married couple. Most of these couples have children. Some families consist only of parents and only (*Ezad Azraai Jamsari et.al, 2004*). According to *Azizi Yahaya (2005)* family background factors that influence the cognition of children or individuals are family shape, family size, family socio-economics, parental education and home atmosphere.

In the family there is already a leader, i.e. the father who acts as the head of the family. The happiness and well -being of a family depends on the role of its parents. Therefore, various social problems that occur among young people are said to stem from problems in the family. Psychological conflict caused by this phenomenon can be seen in the novels of *PPM*, *Manikam Kalbu*, *TTD* and *Bahlut*. In the novel *PPM*, *Faisal Tehrani* shows the conflict that occurs between husband and wife and problems to children due to the relaxation of family ties. This is due to the lack of love, respect and so on between husband and wife. Through her character, *Datin Malini* is described as experiencing stress and mental conflict because she was not treated well by her husband, *Datuk Zuri*. *Datin Malini* suffered mental and physical torture due to *Datuk Zuri's* cold attitude towards her. *Gunjai's* character shows that there is no happiness, causing a family to be on the verge of destruction.

Family socioeconomics refers to a measure of prestige within a particular social group. Usually the socioeconomic status is based on the income of an individual or a person's household. Educational status is also a benchmark to a person's socioeconomic status (Shahabuddin Hashim et.al, 2004). In this context, Faisal Tehrani likes to take the issue of poverty as the cause of mental conflict. This conflict problem is worked on effectively in the novels of PPM, Manikam Kalbu and Bahlut. Poor family conditions result in parents not being able to provide various facilities for their children such as nutritious food, clothing, health, education and perfect basic amenities at home. For example, in the novel PPM, due to the loss of poverty, Jora and Mak Milah experience emotional stress and need to make decisions to ease the burden. Similarly, in the novel Manikam Kalbu, the character Ziriyab experiences a mental conflict because he lives in poverty with his grandmother. The problems and burdens faced by Ziriyab are increasingly felt because his grandmother suffers from amnesia. Therefore, Ziriyab has to take care of and meet the needs of his grandmother. The conflict within Ziriyab continued to be felt when his grandmother died. Ziriyab is described as being in a depressed state thinking about his fate and the future of his life. In Bahlut's novel, Bahlut's character is described as living in poverty and deprivation. Due to poverty, Bahlut suffered from stress so he did not want to continue his schooling. The conflict in Bahlut's soul escalated when his mother was said to have died as a result of being attacked by a tiger.

Peer factor

Peers refer to individuals who are the same or nearly the same age. Relationships with friends will exist on the basis of interests, fields, religions, hobbies, abilities and so on. Nevertheless, problems with peers will exist due to differences in culture, religion, social status, place and thought. It is this situation that is expressed in triggering conflict with peers in Faisal Tehrani's novels. This peer -to -peer psychic conflict can be found in the novels Manikam Kalbu, TTD and Bahlut. In the novel Manikam Kalbu, Ziriyab is described as having problems as a result of the attitude of his schoolmates who mocked, insulted and belittled his interest in the field of sewing. In the novel TTD, on the other hand, it is shown that peers cause conflict as a result of the existence of feelings of love between them. Relationships based on friendship become strained as a result of love for the same friend. This conflict takes place in Salsabila after Kamil and Lam Ping Hai have fallen in love with Salsabila. At the same time, Teh Sofia has fallen in love with Kamil. Proposals and hopes from these two friends left Salsabila in a state of depression and anxiety. Salsabila does not want to hurt the hearts of Teh Sofia, Kamal and Lam Ping Hai because they are her dear friends.

In Manikam Kalbu, the conflict stems from the attitude of Ziriyab's friends who could not accept that he chose to major in sewing. For her friends the major is for women. Her friends often scoffed and looked down on the field of sewing she studied. This situation puts stress and conflict in Ziriyab. Conflict within Ziriyab due to the attitude and actions of a friend became more apparent when he was slandered for sending obscene sms to teacher Natasya. Ziyab could not defend himself because no one believed and gave him a chance to defend himself. Meanwhile, in Bahlut's novel, this conflict occurs between Bahlut and Razak. Razak is a teammate in athletics events. Due to differences in race, religion and social status caused Razak to often insult, issue abusive and sharp words to Bahlut. Bahlut felt sad, disappointed, angry and dilemma with Razak's actions which he could not accept while Bahlut never did anything wrong to Razak.

Political and Social Factors

The leader is the representative of the voice of the people and without the support of the people, it is unlikely that the leader will succeed in forming a political party. However, in the case of fighting for the voice of the people, matters of personal interest must be set aside first. The role of a leader is to fight for the rights and welfare of his society (K. Ramanathan, 1987). This soul conflict stemming from power and politics is highlighted in the novels of PPM, SsPJ, TTD and Bahlut. For example, in the PPM novel, the conflict caused by politics is faced by Datuk Zuri and Tan Sri Yadi. These two political characters experience a soul conflict to seize power, remain as leaders or elected representatives and win the hearts of members in the party as well as the community to support them. Thus, between these two leaders worked together to bring down the opponent and remain in power. In order to maintain their position and power, Datuk Zuri and Tan Sri Yadi looked for each other's weaknesses and tricks to bring down the opponents.

Problems with leaders continue in the TTD novel. This situation was experienced by Salsabila with Datuk Ghaffar. Salsabila was very upset, angry, upset and upset because Datuk Ghaffar could not use his power and position as the people's representative to avoid taking papaya plantations and land of the villagers to carry out development projects. The conflict of the soul with the leader is also revealed in Bahlut's novel. The leader featured in this novel is the attitude of a community leader or leader to the community. The village community hopes that the appointed leader will be able to carry out his duties with full trust, transparency and honesty. Unfortunately the elected leader is selfish, wealthy and willing to conspire to commit fraud to his community. This attitude is highlighted through Batin Endau. Batin Endau's attitude of being involved in illegal logging and persecuting the villagers has caused a conflict with Tiji's father, Bahlut. Tiji was upset and upset with the attitude of Batin Endau who was involved in illegal logging in their settlement area. Moreover, this soul conflict occurs between Bahlut and the authorities or leaders. Bahlut opined that the problem of

illegal logging activities in his village would be difficult to curb as long as the authorities did not intervene. To show his anger, frustration and resentment, Bahlut has taken a firm decision to deal with the problem.

Analysis of manifestations of mental conflict

Faisal Tehrani also shows the manifestations of soul conflict faced by the character in various positive and negative forms. According to Rosenberg and Hovland (1960), an affective reaction is part of an attitude, i.e. a feeling that acts as an evaluative element. Behavior is an element that describes a person's attitude. The attitude shown is a manifestation of emotion. Thus, the manifestations featured in the story will this make the storytelling more interesting, convey the message and expand the story being told. Situations from a character's psychic conflict can be detected through the character's actions, attitudes, behaviors and thoughts. Among the manifestations created are depression and sadness, aggression, transference and awareness and realization.

Depression and Sadness

Depression is a manifestation displayed through conflicting characters. This depression can be detected in the novels of PPM, Manikam Kalbu and Bahlut. In the novels it is shown that almost all the characters who experience conflict are in prolonged and deep grief. These characters are in grief causing emotions, thoughts, attitudes, motivations and behaviors to be disrupted. Their daily lives become unmanageable and imperfect as they bear the grief of the problems that occur. For example, the characters of Haji Chenon, Mak Milah and Jora in the novel PPM who are in grief due to the loss of paddy land which is their source of livelihood. Meanwhile, Chai Yin was in grief after being raped and threatened by Datuk Zuri not to disclose the incident to the authorities. Jenny's character is also in grief and in need after her feelings of love are rejected by Irfan and she decides to live in London.

In the novel Manikam Kalbu, the character of Ziriyab is shown to be a quiet, lonely and depressed person after the death of his grandmother and the accusation of sending pornographic messages to teacher Natasya. Ziriyab turned into a quiet and solitary student after being accused of sending pornographic sms to teacher Natasya. Next, in the TTD novel, this sadness is highlighted through the characters of Salsabila, Teh Sofia, her Aunt or stepmother and Mimi. Their grief stems from the loss of an inheritance, romance and the death of a loved one. Through the novel Bahlut also presents readiness through the character of Bahlut. Bahlut was in grief and melancholy after the death of his mother due to a tiger attack. Bahlut refused to study and wanted to settle in the village. Bahlut is increasingly sad and disappointed to see illegal logging continue in his village. Next, the event of the death of Mak Su Suraya who is considered a successor to his mother has affected the soul of Bahlut. The family of Ustaz Zaidi and his children who are very saddened by the death of Mak Su Suraya who managed their lives all this time also felt sad.

Aggressive

This aggressiveness refers to the effort to realize the frustration experienced. Aggressiveness usually involves physical actions that will affect oneself as well as others (Shahabuddin Hashim et.al, 2004). Aggressive attitudes and traits that are highlighted are anger, revenge and aggressive actions through words, behaviors and deeds. This aggressive attitude can be traced in the novels of PPM, TTD and Bahlut. In the PPM novel, an aggressive attitude is shown through the characters Jenny, Haji Chenon and Mak Milah. Jenny's character shows an aggressive attitude stemming from her conflicts and life experiences. Jenny showed an aggressive attitude such as being willing to fight Datuk Zuri, vindictive towards men and engaging in prostitution to satisfy her desire to live in luxury. Similarly, Mak Milah became aggressive by being willing to fight people who wanted to destroy her paddy fields. For example, Jenny has reacted harshly to Datuk Zuri who committed many atrocities not only on himself but also on the community that supports him. Also, because of her childhood experience of being nearly raped has caused Jenny to become vindictive towards men.

Meanwhile, in the TTD novel, an aggressive attitude is shown on the characters of Salsabila, Shahrizzaman, Kamil and Lam Ping Hai. Salsabila's character is in conflict when his papaya farm will be taken over as a national development site. As a result, Salsabila became aggressive with a brave, resilient attitude and acted decisively to defend his papaya farmland. Salsabila is described as having risen up fighting alone to defend the land and demanding a fair price of compensation from the company that took his paddy land. Shahrizzaman's character, on the other hand, becomes aggressive after engaging in social activities and needs money to live in luxury and pleasure. The obstructed love conflict has made Kamal and Lam Ping Hai quarrel or compete to grab Salsabila. The culmination of their conflict came when Kamil and Lam Ping Hai had a serious quarrel at the Salsabila papaya farm.

In Bahlut novel, this aggressive attitude occurs in the characters of Bahlut and Tiji who try to expose illegal logging activities in their village. After various failed attempts, Bahlut has decided to take tough, decisive and courageous action, which is to throw the gold medal won in the 100 meters event into the Klang River if the government does not want to address the issue of illegal logging in his village.

Transfer

Its next manifestation is transplantation. According to Shahabuddin Hashim et.al (2004) transfer occurs when a person transfers an impulse that has a specific goal to another goal that can be accepted by the surrounding society. This transfer action can be seen in the novels of PPM, SsPJ, Bahlut and TTD. In the PPM novel, this behavior is depicted on the characters of Irfan, Jenny and Haji Chenon. Through the character of Irfan, it is described that he is no longer interested in making love after experiencing the disappointment of love with Kasmariza. Irfan seems to have given up on making love and has rejected the feelings of love from Jenny, Chai Yin and Kasmariza. Irfan's decision was beyond the expectations of Jenny, Chai Yin and Kasmariza. So is Jenny who acts aggressively after dealing with conflict. Jenny has teamed up with Irfan and Chai Yinn to expose the tyranny that Datuk Zuri has committed. Apart from that, Jenny also decided to isolate herself by taking herself to London after Irfan rejected love and felt sorry for Datin Malini's fate which was wasted by Datuk Zuri. Similarly, Jenny has decided to isolate herself after her love was rejected by Irfan and wanted to distance herself from Datuk Zuri. Jenny decided to settle in London. Irfan also decided to resign as a journalist at the Detik newspaper company. Next, Irfan decided to marry Jora and settle in Washington because he wanted to further his studies in the United States. Similarly, the character of Haji Chenon decided to isolate himself by moving to Kelantan. Haji Chenon wanted to live in a hut settlement to get closer to religion. Next, Irfan conveyed his feelings of frustration and reminder to Datuk Zuri by presenting a portrait of Datuk Zuri with a line of sentences that evoked a reminder to Datuk Zuri.

If viewed in SsPJ's novel, this transfer is shown through the character of Ungku Nur. Ungku Nur who is experiencing disappointment, sadness and misery with his marriage and illness decided to break up with Norhishamudin. After the divorce process took place, Ungku Nur decided to separate because he realized that his marriage did not bring happiness as he hoped. Ungku Nur became a resilient, strong and brave person to continue his life. Ungku Nur decided to migrate and settle in Turkey. To get rid of the conflict of his soul, Ungku Nur took to study the history of the state of Johor to be passed on to the new generation, especially the people of the state of Johor. Ungku Nur transferred his feelings of sadness, frustration, heartache and self-suffering by doing a study on the history of the state of Johor during the reign of Sultan Ibrahim and Abu Bakar to be used as a reference for future generations.

Moreover, in Bahlut's novel, this manifestation can be traced through Bahlut's character. The effects of the conflict sparked by Razak who often insulted and looked down on his nation, have evoked the nature of courage, fortitude, courage and perseverance in Bahlut to prove that his nation has equal or greater strength than other nations. For that, Bahlut has fought hard in the 100-meter athletics event. Bahlut's efforts and actions are due to the conflict of the soul that exists within him.

Satisfaction and optimism

This pleasure refers to the change of a conflicted character into a more positive one. This attitude exists after realizing that everything that happens is a divine provision and cannot be changed again. Accordingly, the characters who experience conflict change for the better and regard the problem they face as a life challenge. These changes in attitudes, actions and thoughts can be traced in all of these novels. For example, in the PPM novel, it is shown that the characters Irfan and Haji Chenon realize that the conflict that occurs against them is difficult to deal with. On this realization, Irfan has resigned as a journalist because the principles of employment are contrary to his own tenets. Similarly, Haji Chenon has calmed down with the failure to defend his ancestral land and decided to migrate to Kelantan to get closer to religion.

Next, this change in attitude can be seen in the character of Ungku Nur in the novel SsPJ. Ungku Nur's soul conflict with Norhishamudin has made Ungku Nur more courageous, resilient, aware and calm that what happens to him is a divine decree. Therefore, Ungku Nur decided to separate from living pretending to be happy with her husband. Through the novel TTD, it is portrayed through the character of Salsabila. Salsabila who faced stress and burden with her personal, family and papaya farm problems, had realized and calmed down that it was a trial for her. Salsabila has boldly decided to reject the proposal from Kamal and Lam Phing Hai, instead choosing Sazli as her husband. Similarly, the character of Bahlut in the novel Bahlut who is also aware and transformed into a teenager who is brave to make decisions, resilient and persistent to change his future. Bahlut has become a teenager who excel in their studies and proved that the children of the original can also be successful in all fields if given the opportunity and support.

6.1.3. MENTAL CONFLICT RESOLUTION ANALYSIS

Faisal Tehrani wants to convey useful messages and values through his novels. Every problem and conflict that is triggered will be resolved in order to provide guidance and satisfaction to the readership. In order to realize his noble wish, Faisal Tehrani is seen doing various ways to resolve conflicts or problems that he is working on. Among the ways of resolving the conflict of the soul that is triggered is success or happiness, return to the teachings of religion, no dissolution or end and death.

a. Happiness and success

For conflicts that achieve success and happiness can be seen in the novels *Manikam Kalbu*, *TTD* and *Bahlut*. In the novel *Manikam Kalbu*, it is shown that the problems faced by Ziryab can be solved as well as possible. All the causes of her conflict with her ambitions, defamation cases and the death of her grandmother can be overcome. Ziryab has become a successful student and will be able to further his studies abroad in the field of sewing or will become a fashion designer once he graduates. Similarly, in the *TTD* novel, Salsabila and Teh Sofia are shown to be able to achieve their ambition to become successful papaya entrepreneurs. All personal problems and problems in papaya cultivation such as the problem of obtaining compensation claims and the problem of operating a papaya farm can be overcome. Salsabila and Teh Sofia were not only successful in the papaya business but were able to build a happy family. In *Bahlut*, it is shown that Bahlut has managed to rediscover his mother who is said to have been killed by a tiger. In addition, Bahlut managed to attract the attention of the country's top leaders to tackle the problem of illegal logging in his village.

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b. Religious beliefs

Religion is a guide and a guide for all mankind. Therefore all human beings have a particular religion or belief. The religion that is held in Faisal Tehrani's novels is Islam. In line with his religiously educated background, Faisal Tehrani has indeed made religious teachings one of the values inculcated in his novels either directly or covertly. Faisal Tehrani would like to remind that religious teachings need to be practiced and become a human hand in his life. Thus, it is depicted that conflicting characters have chosen religion as a way to alleviate or resolve problems within themselves. For example, in the novel *PPM*, Datuk Zuri is described as living in luxury and pleasure, but still facing conflict as a result of his actions. To relieve stress and feelings, Datuk Zuri performed umrah to obtain forgiveness for the sins he had committed. Similarly, Haji Chenon, has chosen to settle in a hut in Kelantan to draw closer to Allah S.W.T. having had nothing else in the village of Jentayu.

Next, religion becomes the choice and the character's hold is shown through the character of Ungku Nur in the novel *SsPJ*. After realizing that he could not live longer due to cancer, Ungku Nur decided to separate and settle in Turkey. Ungku Nur wanted to spend the rest of his life in Turkey and do research on the history of the state of Johor once upon a time. Ungku Nur calmed down with the fate that befell him and was ready to face his death. Before it was too late, Ungku Nur had sent a letter to all her sisters, brothers, fathers and ex-husbands to apologize and allow her to leave for Turkey. Ungku Nur is not saddened by his fate, but is full of optimism and strives to complete a study on the Johor state government for the public, especially the people of Johor.

Similarly, Salsabila in the novel *TTD* has performed istiqharah prayers to get clues as to whether to choose Kamil or Lam Ping Hai as his life partner. Salsabila did so as a last resort to resolve the deadlock and feud between Kamil and Lam Ping Hai who did not want to give up on choosing him as their life partner. The same goes for his stepmother who is getting closer to religion after her deteriorating physical condition and cancer. Meanwhile in the novel *Manikam Kalbu*, the characters Ziryab and Manikam Kalbu who have trouble producing real clothes or fashions or do not bring sin to themselves and the society who wear them. To address the problem, Ziryab has received guidance from Ustaz Asmadi on the characteristics of clothes that should be produced and worn by women. Ultimately, by fulfilling the teachings and requirements of religion, all problems in life can be solved in the best way.

Overall, the study shows that Faisal Tehrani reveals various values and problems in his novels related to human beings. He showed concern for the events that took place whether based on his experience, observations, readings and research. Accordingly, his novels can be analyzed in a variety of approaches or purposes. The psychological aspect is another element that is clearly expressed in his novels. This psychological aspect shows that he is an author who has mastered various knowledge and skills in making his novels interesting and distinctive. Worked psychic conflicts show conflicts

that are definitely experienced by everyone regardless of age, gender, race and so on. This conflict occurs due to internal and external factors or its environment. In this study it is shown that external factors influence psychic conflict more than internal factors. This is because everyone cannot live alone and needs to face, socialize, deal, face and be with others. Therefore, there will be conflicts or problems due to differences of opinion, ideas, culture, religion, employment, education and so on. This is the situation that is worked on quite firmly and interestingly in Faisal Tehrani's novels.

Faisal Tehrani shows that there are differences in conflict between teenagers, adults and the elderly. Psychological conflicts experienced by adolescents are more to problems about personal needs, love, ambition and romance as well as family. This is what is revealed in the novel *Manikam Kalbu* and *Bahlut*. Meanwhile, the youth or the elderly face mental conflict due to internal and external problems such as personal problems, responsibilities, environment, romance, friendship, employment, finance and household. This soul conflict is expressed in the novels *PPM*, *SsPJ* and *TTD*. Psychological conflict experienced by an individual will have its own impact in terms of attitudes, actions, behaviors and thoughts. Some of the manifestations worked out as a result of conflict by the characters are positive and negative attitudes. Among the obvious manifestations presented are depression, sadness, aggression, complacency and optimism. These changes in attitudes are temporary and prolonged depending on the type of conflict you want to convey.

Next, Faisal Tehrani's creativity in authorship can be highlighted through the method of resolution or resolution to the conflicts of the soul that is worked on. The solution applied is happiness and success as well as a return to religious beliefs. As for the aspect of happiness resolution can be found in the novels *Manikam Kalbu*, *TTD* and *Bahlut*. For the conflict back to the teachings of religion is shown in the novels *PPM* and *SsPJ*. Faisal Tehrani does not commit cruelty or end the conflict of his characters in a way that could provoke dissatisfaction or criticism to the reader. This is in line with his religiously educated, intellectual and highly career background. Ultimately, Faisal Tehrani's ability to create varied conflicts in the novels shows a high power of sensitivity and creativity in him. In fact, it can be highlighted that Aisal Tehrani has never run out of ideas and resources to produce quality and knowledgeable novels for the eyes of his readers.

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